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Buckling optimization of variable-axial composite laminates with non-linear geometry

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Abstract: Unlike conventional laminates with constant orientation along with the plate, Variable-axial (VA) laminates have a stiffness that varies according to the coordinate. This type of laminate can have its characteristics improved instability by choosing its orientation properly, improving its efficiency. The objective of this work is to optimize the critical buckling load in VA laminate plate. Due to the difficulty of modelling the VA laminate analytically, it used the finite element method (FEM) with the subroutine for the implicit User Material model (UMAT). For the optimization process, to maximize the critical buckling load, using the genetic algorithm (GA). Better results of the buckling load were obtained using the bilinear polynomial, compared to the biquadratic, bicubic, and linear variation present in the literature considering the restrictions of the manufacturing process Automated Fiber Placement (AFP).

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, the demand for materials has been increasing considerably in the aerospace, aeronautics, energy, and marine sectors [1]. In the aeronautical industry, replacement and combined materials with high mechanical strength, specific weight, high durability, and good corrosion resistance are substitutes [2].

One way to improve the performance of carbon fiber reinforced polymeric laminates (CFRP) materials is the use of variable axial (VA), where these laminates have significantly increased the range of designs available to engineers, in which their fabrication was only possible. due to recent advances in manufacturing processes that have led to the possibility of directing fibers in the plane of a layer [3]. In this type of laminate, it has been proven

that it is possible to increase its fundamental frequency [4], the flutter response [5], and buckling [6-9]. An important variation is linear, eq. (1), defined by [10]:

$$\theta(x') = \phi' + \frac{2(T_1 - T_0)}{a} |x'| + \theta_0 \tag{1}$$

Where the parameters ϕ', T_0 and T_1 are respectively the angle between the coordinate axes, the angle at the center of the plate, and the angle of the board edges, in fig. (1), representation is given by $[\phi' \pm \langle T_0 | T_1 \rangle]$.

Fig 1. Laminate with variable axial.

1.1. Non-linear variation of angle orientation

Another way to vary the fiber angle, but in a non-linear way using a Lagrange’s Orthogonal Polynomials (LOP), eq. (2), for an interpolation of the fiber orientation angle, as a function of the control angles T_{mn} , for a mesh with $M \times N$ pre-selected control points.

Fig. 2. Control points for LOP (a) Bilinear, (b) Biquadratic and (c) bicubic.

$$\theta(x, y) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} T_{mn} \prod_{m \neq i} \left(\frac{x - x_i}{x_m - x_i} \right) \prod_{n \neq j} \left(\frac{y - y_j}{y_n - y_j} \right) \tag{2}$$

The LOP is interesting because it allows variation in both directions, allowing a high stiffness variation compared to linear variation, the control points, and their positions are report in fig. 2 for the bi-linear, bi-quadratic, and bi-cubic polynomial.

1.2. Curvature Restriction

In this work, the AFP process is considered [11], where it has gained notoriety for producing complex surfaces with high productivity, a constraint of this process is the radius of curvature ρ , which must be greater than 635 mm for a tape width of 3.175 mm [8]. Therefore, the manufacturing constraint, eq (3), must be established as a function of the deposition path s .

$$\frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{d\theta}{ds} = \frac{\partial\theta}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{ds} + \frac{\partial\theta}{\partial y} \frac{dy}{ds} \tag{3}$$

With dx and dy the component of decomposition of s in directions x and y respectively.

1.3. Buckling Analysis

The critical buckling load, boils down to the solution of a potential energy minimization problem, which is equivalent to eq. (4):

$$\{[K] - \lambda[K_g]\}\{A\} = \{0\} \tag{4}$$

Where $[K]$ is the global stiffness matrix, $[K_g]$ is the geometric stiffness matrix, associated with external stresses, λ the eigenvalues, and $\{A\}$ the eigenvectors associated with the buckling modes.

The critical buckling load N_{cr} is determined, in the first eigenvalue following eq (5), as a function of the initial load applied N_0 .

$$N_{cr} = \lambda_1 N_0 \tag{5}$$

2. Methodology

Due to the difficulties of modeling a VA laminate analytically, the FEM software ABAQUS™ linked to subroutine (UMAT) for to determine the critical buckling load. The optimization model is a square plate with four plates and stacking sequence $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\theta_3/\theta_4]$, simply supported, with a compressive load, fig. 3, the parameters a , d and N_0 are respectively 1000 mm, 100 mm, 1 N/mm, and the total thickness h is 1 mm.

Fig. 3. Square plate with hole (SSSS) with restricted transverse edges under compressive load

2.1. Optimization algorithm

To optimize the critical buckling load, an optimization algorithm GA based on Neo-Darwinism [12] will be used. To reach this objective, the design variables are the control points T'_{mn} according to the linear variation, shown in eq. (1), and the LOP, eq (2), subject to the manufacturing constraint of the critical radius of curvature, eq. (3) considered in the AFP process. Then the optimization problem reduces to:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Maximize : } N_{cr}(T_{mn}) = \text{Buckling Load} \left[\frac{N}{mm} \right] \\ \text{Subject: Radius of curvature } (\rho) \geq 635 \text{ mm} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In GA, the crossover and mutation parameters used were 0.7 and 0.04, also due to the high complexity, a population and generations respectively $20n$ and $10n$, where n is the number of variables.

3. Results and Discussions

In the numerical results presented here, four layers were used, according to the variation shown in eq. (1) and eq. (3), the properties of the material are $E_1 = 127 \text{ GPa}$, $E_2 = 10 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.44 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{23} = 3.05 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.34$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.306$. The mesh contains 2080 elements and linear interpolation, with sizes ranging from 50 mm nearby to the edge and 10 mm to the hole.

Table 1 represents the results regarding the optimization of the model illustrated in the methodology, show in fig 2. In this table the linear and non-linear variation results are compared with the straight fiber optimization. The variation according to the LOP presented better results compared to the linear variation proposed in [6]. Better results were expected for LOP with higher order, as shown in [7], but in the cases studied, the curvature constraint, eq (3) is not met for high variations from this polynomial, then the best result was obtained using a bilinear polynomial.

Table 1. Critical buckling load optimization for linear and non-linear variation with 4 layers.

Model	Nº of optimized variables	N_{cr} [N/mm]	Gain
$[0]_{4s}$		0.1006	
Linear Variation	6	0.1250	24.3%
Bi linear	8	0.1396	38.8%
biquadratic	18	0.1288	28.0%
bicubic	32	0.1286	27.8%

Fig. 4. The better results of the optimization were obtained using bilinear LOP (a) layer 1 and 4. (b) Layer 2 and 3.

The orientation of the optimal result, for layer 1 and 2, show be in fig 4. Angles close to zero degrees observed in their center, the fact occurs because due to the first buckling mode, the critical displacement is at the center of

the plate, a high stiffness, in the direction of loading. On the other hand, larger angles are found near the edges, reducing the stiffness in the orientation of loading, this effect is beneficial, as it allows high energy absorption at the edges, increasing the critical buckling load.

4. Conclusions

The advantage of developing the algorithm using FEM, is in the flexibility of modifying the parameters, so it is possible to easily vary them and implement new functions, such as shape functions and polynomials for the orientation of the plate. In addition, the LOP provided high improvements to the critical buckling load, however, polynomials with high degrees lead to great variation in curvature, this fact is an obstacle in relation to fabrication using the AFP, therefore an improvement in regarding allowable curvature or the use of fabrication methods that allow high curvature should be investigated.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Credits author statement

Netto, J.V.N: Conceptualization; Methodology; results; Original draft writing. **Tita V.:** Resources; review. **Ribeiro M.L.:** review; Supervision.

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References

- [1] Almeida, J. H. S.; Ribeiro, M. L.; Tita, V.; Amico, S. C.; “Stacking sequence optimization in composite tubes under internal pressure based on a genetic algorithm accounting for progressive damage,” *Composite Structures*, vol. 178, pp. 20–26, 2017.
- [2] Roeseler, W.G.; SARH B.; KISMARTON, M.U. Composite structures: the first 100 years. Presented at: 16th International Conference on Composite Materials; Kyoto, Japan. 2007.
- [3] Ribeiro, P.; Akhavan, H.; Teter, A.; Warmański, J. A review on the mechanical behavior of curvilinear fiber composite laminated panels. *Journal of Composite Materials*, v. 48, n. 22, p. 2761–2777. 2014.
- [4] Abdalla, M. M.; Setoodeh, S.; Gürdal, Z. Design of variable stiffness composite panels for maximum fundamental frequency using lamination parameters. *Composite Structures*, v. 81, n. 2, p. 283–291. 2007.
- [5] Guimarães, T. A. M., *Contribuição ao Estudo do Comportamento Dinâmico e Aeroelástico de Laminados de Rigidez Variável*. 2016. 134 f. Doctoral Thesis, Federal University of Uberlândia, Uberlândia. 2014.
- [6] Gürdal, Z.; Tatting, B.; Wu, C. “Variable stiffness composite panels: Effects of stiffness variation on the in-plane and buckling response” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, v. 39, n. 5, p. 911 – 922, 2008. ISSN 1359-835X.

- [7] Wu, Z.; Weaver, P. M.; Raju, G.; Kim, B. C. Buckling analysis and optimization of variable angle tow composite plates. *Thin-Walled Structures*, v. 60, p. 163–172, 11 2012.
- [8] BLOM, A. W. Structural performance of fiber placed variable-stiffness composite conical and cylindrical shells, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Delft, 2010.
- [9] Netto, J. V. B.; Ribeiro, M. L.; Sartorato, M.; Tita, V. Buckling optimization in variable stiffness composite laminated. In: 5th Brazilian Conference on Composite Materials, 2021, S CARLOS. Proceedings of 5th Brazilian Conference on Composite Materials, 2021.
- [10] GÜRDAL Z., OLMEDO R. In-plane response of laminates with spatially varying fiber orientations - Variable stiffness concept. *AIAA Journal* (1993) 31:4, 751-758, 1993.
- [11] Brasington A, Sacco C, Halbritter J, Wehbe R, Harik R. "Automated fiber placement: A review of history, current technologies, and future paths forward". *Composites Part C: Open Access*, Vol. 6, pp 100182, 2021, 10.1016/j.jcomc.2021.100182.
- [12] MITCHELL, M. An introduction to genetic algorithms. [S.l.]: MIT Press. 1998.